

EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBES CONTENT ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF PP/EPDM/MWCNT BLEND NANOCOMPOSITES UNDER DYNAMIC AND QUASI-STATIC LOADING

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Interconnected MWCNTs network

Dynamic loading (Impact strength)

Quasi-Static loading (EWF)

SEM images of EWF fractured surfaces of PP/EPDM/MWCNT with a) 0.5 wt%, b) 1 wt%, c) 2 wt% and d) 3 wt%.

SEM images of impact fractured surfaces of a) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/0.5), b) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/1/0.5), c) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/1), d) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/2/1), e) PP/EPDM/MWCNT (80/20/3) and f) PP/EPDM/PP-g-MA/MWCNT (80/20/6/3)

MWCNT phase has negative effects on the fracture toughness through hindrance effect on the matrix fibril yielding